

THE THEORETICAL BASIS OF CREDIT POLICY OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES AND COMMERCIAL BANKS

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ABSTRACT

ensuring the level of diversification of the credit portfolio in conditions of deepening specialization of the activities of commercial banks becomes a complex issue. Because, in such conditions, the bulk of loans issued by a commercial bank will accumulate in one area or network. In the credit policy of commercial banks, credit risk management plays an important role. Currently, the assessment and management requirements developed by the Basel Committee in credit risk management are widely used in international banking practice.

In the strategy for reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025, it is recognized as the priority directions for reforming the country's banking system to carry out lending only on market terms, improve the quality of credit portfolio management, and follow a moderate increase in lending volumes.

According to the conclusions of O Yastrebova and a Subbotins, the instability of the financial status of small business entities operating in the agrarian sector and the low level of solvency prevent them from increasing the level of access to the financial services of credit institutions, including microfinance services.

According to N Figurovskaya, the process of lending small business entities should be financially supported by the state. The main focus in this should be on the allocation of resources from the state budget and on Boniface[1].

A Staxnyuk's conclusion that the main problems associated with increasing the level of use of commercial bank loans of small business entities are as follows::

- insufficient development of a small business support mechanism;
- low quality of collateral objects;
- the fact that the client is not transparent ("khufyona" is a high level of income; insufficient reliable resources necessary for an objective assessment of the client's financial condition, his or her creditworthiness; the absence of turnover on current accounts; the fact that the main flows of income are passing in cash, etc.);
- insufficient economic (financial) knowledge (low quality of business plans; lending goals, the absence of a clear understanding of the essence of banking products, experience in working with the bank; incompleteness of accounting, etc.);

- insufficient resources, especially cheap and long-term ones, necessary for investments in the real sector of the economy for more than a year;
- the fact that the lack of improvement in the legislation on the protection of the rights of creditors does not allow banks to finance high-risk transactions.[2]

According to Uzbek economist a Baymurotov, there are three approaches to increasing the ability of agricultural enterprises to use commercial bank loans, and it is the third approach, that is, the difference between the preferential interest rate of loans issued by banks to agricultural enterprises and the market rate of bank loans paid by the state to commercial banks, is considered a relatively effective approach[4].

Q Toshmatov studied the issue of lending agriculture by banks and, based on the results of the study, comes to the conclusion that: "it is necessary to create a system of effective lending of working capital and fixed assets necessary for farms to grow other agricultural products, in addition to the crop of cotton and grain grown for state needs, and gradually transfer to preferential lending farms, which are being loaned at the expense of the accounting fund of agricultural products purchased for state needs, directly from special

Prof. According to a Vakhobov, it is necessary to Bonify the interest rates of investment loans issued by banks to small business entities for the purpose of establishing production enterprises and firms specializing in the processing of agricultural products in rural areas at the expense of the Fund for Reconstruction and development of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2].

Commercial banks are one of the main issues of credit policy and are the management of the loan portfolio.

An effective management strategy is widely used in the management of the credit portfolio of commercial banks. This strategy includes:

- formation of the optimal composition of the loan portfolio by the levels of risk and profitability;
- ensure compliance of the state of the credit portfolio with the current state of the national economy;
- monitoring on the quality of the loan portfolio.

The process of managing a loan portfolio is directly related to the formation of a loan portfolio, which allows strategic and tactical management of a commercial bank. This is explained, Firstly, by the fact that commercial bank loans are an important source of financing the activities of business entities, and secondly, by the high share of interest income from loans in the gross income of commercial banks.

The lower limit on the profitability of the loan portfolio is determined by the sum of the costs of performing credit operas and the interest paid to the resources involved. Therefore, in maintaining a low and stable level of credit valuation, the cost of credit operas and the valuation of the resources involved plays an important role. It should be noted that in countries with high inflation rates, the possibility of lowering the interest rates of commercial bank loans is limited. This is because, firstly, commercial banks take into account the inflation rate when setting interest rates on loans, and secondly, the central bank cannot lower its refinancing rate in conditions of high inflation rates. Liquidity of the portfolio plays an important role in the management of the credit portfolio of commercial banks.

The liquidity of a loan portfolio is determined, first of all, by the quality of the loan

portfolio. That is, timely and complete repayment of loans serves to increase the bank's liquidity level, while ensuring the quality of the loan portfolio.

It should be noted that the liquidity of a loan portfolio directly affects the financial stability of a commercial bank. This effect is manifested in the following directions:

- an increase in the amount of problematic loans leads to an increase in the amount of interest-bearing expenses (Reserve deductions intended to cover losses from loans are taken to the cost of the full bank);
- failure to return loans on time unclassified loans will lead to tarkby's deterioration;
- the amount of expired interest accrued on loans with the status of not growing interest is deducted from the balance sheet of commercial banks, and as a result, the amount of interest income is reduced.

It is worth noting that the effectiveness of the management of the credit portfolio of commercial banks is strongly influenced by the degree of diversification of the credit portfolio. The low level of diversification of the loan portfolio increases the likelihood of an increase in the level of credit risk. A new approach called the "standardized approach" to credit risk assessment was proposed by the Basel Committee in 2004 (Table 1).

Table 1.
Standardized approach to credit risk assessment

Credit rating	AAA AA -	A+ A -	BBB+ BB-	BB- дан паст	Unrated
Risk level	20%	50%	100%	150%	100%

source: International Convergence of Capital Measurement and Capital Standards: a Revised Framework. Available at: <http://www.bis.org/publ/bcbs118.htm>.

Table 1 data shows that according to a standardized approach, the level of credit risk is determined depending on the credit rating of the client who received the loan: the higher the client's credit rating, the lower the credit risk level. From the data presented in Table 1, it can be seen that according to the standardized approach, loans with a risk level of 150% appeared. That is, the risk level of loans to customers with a credit rating below VV is 150 percent. Table 1 data shows that the risk level of a loan given to a client whose credit rating is not available is set at 100%.

In our opinion, a standardized approach leads to a decrease in the level of credit risk in the activities of commercial banks. Because, any commercial bank will try to give a loan to a client with a high credit rating. Because, firstly, there will be a high probability of timely and complete return of loans to customers with a high credit rating, and secondly, a decrease in loans with a low credit risk level will make it possible to increase the adequacy of the regulatory capital of a commercial bank. The adequacy of the regulatory capital of commercial banks is determined by dividing the regulatory capital into the risky sum of the bank's assets.

It is worth noting that in ensuring the adequacy of the capital of commercial banks, it is of paramount practical importance to ensure the proportionality between the growth rate of regulatory capital and the growth rate of the risky sum of bank assets. In addition, it is also important to ensure that the capital structure complies with the requirements of the Basel standard in ensuring the adequacy of

banks' capital. For example, the inclusion of the devaluation Reserve as part of the capital of commercial banks is not possible under the requirements of the Basel standard.

One of the important issues of commercial banking credit policy is undoubtedly the identification of factors affecting asset portfolios and the assessment of their impact. The deterioration of macroeconomic conjuncture leads to a decrease in the volume of production of goods and services, or to a failure to sell the goods produced. Both cases increase the likelihood of non-return of loans issued by commercial banks to companies.

The monetary policy implemented by the central bank has a strong influence on the practice of managing the credit portfolio of commercial banks. This effect is evident in the following areas:

1. An increase in the refinancing rate of the central bank will lead to an increase in the interest rates of commercial bank loans. As a result of this, the likelihood of non-return of commercial bank loans increases. Because, the interest rates of loans are the cost of the loan. The higher the credit valuation, the higher the likelihood that it will not return. The central bank's reduction in the refinancing rate will lead to a decrease in the interest rate of commercial bank loans.

2. The central bank's increase in mandatory reserve rates reduces the possibility of commercial banks lending, while leading to a decrease in the liquidity of banks.

3. An increase in the central bank's refinancing rate reduces the ability of commercial banks to take advantage of the central bank's refinancing loans. This creates a negative impact on their liquidity, resulting in a decrease in banks' ability to make loans. The change in Budget-Tax Policy is one of the important external factors affecting the practice of managing the credit portfolio of commercial banks. In particular, an increase in budget costs leads to a decrease in interest rates of commercial bank loans.

Also, the change in tax policy affects the financial position of customers of commercial banks, and as a result, the impact on the repayment process of commercial bank loans occurs.

An increase in the state budget deficit creates a negative impact on the practice of managing the credit portfolio of commercial banks. This effect is manifested in the following directions:

- an increase in the amount of the state budget deficit forces the government to cover part of the deficit at the expense of loans from the Central Bank, and as a result, the supply of resources in the National loan capital market decreases, and the interest rates of loans increase;

- an increase in the state budget deficit will lead to an increase in inflation rates, and as a result, interest rates of loans from commercial banks will rise;

- the deficit of the state budget leads to a decrease in the amount of loans guaranteed by the government.

Within the factors affecting the practice of managing the credit portfolio of banks, the credit risk management system plays an important role. In transnational banks, the credit risk management system has been improved, allowing this system to prevent the deepening of credit risk.

The level of improvement of the credit solvency assessment system of clients of commercial banks plays an important role in ensuring the effectiveness of the management of the loan portfolio.

In international banking practice, two methods are mainly used when assessing the creditworthiness of clients of commercial banks:

- method of financial coefficients;
- method of assessing cash flow.

It is characteristic that in banking practice of developed countries, great attention is paid to the use of the method of assessing the flow of money when assessing the creditworthiness of customers. This method determines a customer's eligibility for credit payment by dividing their total cash flow into total debt obligations.

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